

ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY OF FUNCTIONAL LITERACY OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING CHEMISTRY

¹Yusupova N.A., ²Shernazarov I.E.

¹Doctoral student of TSPU named after Nizamy

²TSPU named after Nizamy, d.p.s. DSc, acting professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13917349>

Abstract. *The given article presents the analysis of the methodology for assessing the functional literacy of students in the process of teaching chemistry. Changes in the education system include thematic resources, conducting scientific research, assessing students' knowledge in accordance with the requirements of the time, assessing students' functional literacy, as well as information on types of functional literacy.*

Keywords: *functional literacy, analytical-synthetic, comparative-contrastive, analogy, modeling, diagnostic, expert, contextual.*

It is important to suggest that global socio-economic changes occurring in the world, including changes in the education system, special attention to natural science literacy in the practice of training intellectually competent, talented, creatively thinking specialists, are the focus of international assessment studies. At the same time, integrative activities will be carried out that will unite various modern approaches to organizing the educational process of teachers, and therefore, will direct natural science literacy and creative thinking of students to practice, will allow to form functional literacy of students in the education system. In particular, the international assessment programs implemented by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) emphasized the need for widespread use of scientific achievements and innovation in the education system, and changes to the education system.

Definitely, it is recognized that education in all developed countries is a social process that actively influences the domestic policy of the country. The activities of a large number of scientific institutions carrying out pedagogical scientific research in developed countries are aimed at improving educational programs. Effective research is carried out to ensure that qualitative changes in the field of education comply with international educational requirements, develop students' reading, mathematical, scientific literacy and creative thinking for their participation in international assessment programs and achievement of positive results. Therefore, it is recommended to conduct research aimed at implementing an educational environment that creates conditions for students to use their competencies, realize their abilities, creativity and initiative.

According to the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated January 28, 2022 "Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", significant work is being carried out to improve and enhance the knowledge and skills of teaching staff at the international level, as well as the prospects for national development. In the system of continuous education of our country, reforms are being carried out in the system of general secondary education aimed at ensuring the development of modern competencies, which

provides for the formation of educational competencies in students based on advanced foreign experience. One of the priority tasks was set as "Radical improvement of the quality of general secondary education, in-depth study of other important and popular subjects, such as chemistry, biology."

Besides that, the implementation of reforms in all areas, monitoring of results, determining the effectiveness of educational policies in countries based on international rankings and the effective use of international research open up new opportunities.

The research was carried out according to the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan, PD-N.5538[2], dated September 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the public education management system", PD-N.5712[3] on "Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", PR-N.4884 dated April 29, 2019 "Additional measures to improve the education system in Uzbekistan", PR-N.3931, dated September 5, 2018 "On measures to implement the principles of public education management" [5], Resolution N. 997 [6] of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 8, 2018 "On measures to organize international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in the public education system" and other regulatory documents related to this area.

In the education system of developed countries, special attention is paid to the issue of improving the quality of education and proper participation in international assessment processes. Of great importance is the expansion of the ecological and humanitarian didactic sphere for future generations by ensuring the humanitarian principle of the educational paradigm, the formation of natural science literacy in young people, fully demonstrating the development of human ideas (personal ideas) in the teacher and student, which are at the center of competence-based approaches in pedagogical practice, are assessed during its implementation. From this point of view, it is necessary to improve the quality and effectiveness of education, monitor it on the basis of international assessment programs, and create theoretical and methodological support for improving the criteria for assessing creativity.

What is more important, the international assessment of changes in education and research in the world is expanding on the basis of such programs as TALIS, CIVIC, ICCS (International CIVIC and Citizenship Education Study). One of the striking manifestations of such a pedagogical phenomenon, which is acquiring social significance, is the study of the scientific, theoretical and conceptual foundations of the use of international assessment systems in the educational process, the development of theoretical and practical aspects of diagnosing subject competencies of students based on the use of national assessment systems. Also, in countries where the education system is rapidly developing, large-scale scientific research is being carried out to develop the creative and professional creativity of teaching staff, organizing their innovative activities to improve the quality of education. In particular, the Australian Consortium of Educational Research (AGER), the US Educational Testing Service (ETS) and the Japanese National Institute of Educational Research (NER) use modern methods based on STEAM, STRIM and SMART technologies to assess the improvement of professional competence of teaching staff in accordance with the principles of implementation which is becoming increasingly important. Of particular relevance is the increase in the level, development of creative and logical thinking skills of students, thereby contributing to the improvement of the quality of education. PISA and TIMSS,

in addition to determining the knowledge of students and the quality of education in the country, assess the potential of the younger generation. Taking into account the fact that 15-year-old students will actively enter the country's labor market in the near future and become the main capital, the results of the study will be able to predict the future competitiveness of the country.

Surprisingly, the new system for monitoring the assessment of the quality of education in Uzbekistan, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated January 28, 2022, PD-N.60 "Strategy for the further development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", a system based on identification and comparison using international assessment programs is being formed.

Additionally, the use of international studies on the assessment of the quality of education is aimed at monitoring the quality of education based on mutual cooperation of teachers and students of educational institutions, employees of the education system and parents, raising their awareness and enriching their knowledge, imagination in this area.

In the message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to Oliy Majlis, among the pressing issues of state and public importance, special attention was paid to the issue of improving the quality of education and proper preparation for international assessment processes. The result of this study is based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-N.60, dated January 28, 2022 "On the Strategy for the Further Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", PD-N.6108 dated November 6, 2020 "New Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", Decree PD-N.134, dated May 11, 2022 "On measures to develop the sphere of education and science in the period 2022-2026", PD-N.289, dated June 21 "On measures to improve the quality of pedagogical education and further development of the activities of higher educational institutions" and other regulatory documents related to this activity.

Definitely, rapid reform and development of the education system is based on the requirements of building the Third Renaissance in our republic, development of talent, cognitive knowledge, creative abilities of students based on scientific research conducted by teachers, provision of quality education taking into account their interests and needs, formation of creative abilities of young people. Based on the results of international research, the national education system is being reformed, and the research results serve to improve the content of education (methods of teaching and assessing subject concepts, curricula and topics), training programs and advanced training of students, teachers and the creation of new generation textbooks. This is based on pedagogical monitoring of the assessment of natural and scientific literacy of students using PISA and TIMSS tasks, enrichment of teachers' and students' understanding of international assessment systems, preparation for international education.

The level study of the problem. Identification of the talent of students of comprehensive schools, formation and development of creative competence are given attention in a number of studies and scientific papers; the development of basic and scientific-technical competencies of schoolchildren and students was studied in the scientific researches of M. Vakhobov, M. A. Yuldashev, U. Inoyatov, as well as issues of determining their logical thinking skills and increasing their creative abilities on this basis, diagnostics of the level of knowledge – in scientific works of N. Azizkhodzhaeva, B. Khodzhaev, U. Sodikov.

The relevance of the problem in assessing the quality of education is clearly demonstrated by studies conducted in the theory and practice of domestic and foreign education. Thus, in recent years, much attention has been paid to such issues as disclosing the essence of the concept of

quality of education. In Russia, several scientists have conducted scientific research in this area. For example: disclosing the essence of the concept of quality of education (V.P. Bespalko, G.A. Bordovsky, B.G. Gershunsky, V.P. Panasyuk, M.M. Potashnik, N.A. Selezneva and others), on pedagogical qualimetry (A.I. Su-Betto), the quality of knowledge and skills of students (E.A. Krasnovsky, T.L. Kogan and Y. Lerner, M.N. Skatkin, etc.), a leveled approach to teaching students (O.E. Lebedev, L.M. Perminova, A.P. Tryapitsina, etc.), monitoring and diagnostics of the quality of education (B.P. Bitinas, V.V. Guzeev, I. Yu. Gutnik, V.A. Kalney, V.N. Maksimova, A.N. Mayorov, S.E. Shishov, A.P. Tryapitsina, etc.), assessment of student achievements (V.M. Blinov, V. Pisarev, V.M. Polonsky, A.N. Mayorov, etc.), competency-based approach (I.Yu. Aleksashina, O.V. Akulova, V.A. Kalney, S.P. Pisareva, S.B. Shishov, etc.).

Also, numerous works have been carried out by foreign researchers (K. Ingenkamp, I. Costa, R. Wollseller, D. Nixon, G. Cavelti, M. Holt, etc.).

The objectives of the research: the problem, purpose, and hypothesis of the research gave rise to the following specific objectives:

analysis of the state of the problem of assessing the functional literacy of students in the methodological and psychological-pedagogical literature and practice;

determination of its qualitative parameters for determining the level of assessment of functional literacy;

determination of the methodological features of assessing functional literacy and creation of a quality monitoring model on its basis;

development of a methodology for assessing the quality of functional literacy of students according to their preferences using the technology of monitoring the quality of students' knowledge;

testing experimentally the effectiveness of the developed methodology for assessing the quality of functional literacy and provision of recommendations for its use in educational practice.

The subject of the study is the content, component structure, functions, organizational and pedagogical conditions, methods and means of developing a method for assessing the functional literacy of students in the process of teaching chemistry based on the integration of natural sciences.

Research methods. The given study included interviews, questionnaires, theoretical (analytical and synthetic, comparative, analogy, modeling), diagnostic (surveys, testing, observation), prognostic (expert assessment, generalization) and mathematical and statistical analysis (statistical data processing, monitoring results) and pedagogical experimental methods.

The scientific novelty of the study is as follows:

In the theory and methodology of chemical education, to determine the level of assessment of students' functional literacy in chemistry, a context of its qualitative parameters has been developed based on a competency-based integrative approach.

The methodological features of the assessment of the results of chemical education based on functional literacy have been clarified, a model for monitoring the quality of knowledge has been created by modernizing the methodology for assessing students' creative thinking and creating a modern methodology for assessing republican universities in chemistry;

using the technology for monitoring the quality of students' knowledge, the methodology for assessing the quality of students' functional literacy in subjects has been determined, the methodological and theoretical foundations of the methodology for assessing students of the

republic's universities, as well as methodological approaches, leading ideas and methods have been developed;

as a result of experimental testing of the effectiveness of the developed methodology for assessing the quality of functional literacy and recommendations for its use in educational practice, didactic materials for scientifically based organizational and pedagogical conditions, as well as pedagogical models used to develop, diagnose methods and technologies of teaching have been improved

By summarising it should be suggested that the study of the criteria for assessing students and making changes to these criteria in accordance with the requirements of the time is one of the most pressing problems in the education system at present time as during the research, there was conducted study activities in order to partially eliminate these problems and introduce some forms of criteria into practice.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated January 28, 2022 PD-N.60 on the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 <https://lex.uz/docs/http://lex.uz/ru/docs/5841063>
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018. PD-N.5538 "On additional measures to improve the public education management system". <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-3893445>
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 N. PD-N.5712 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-4312785>
4. Decision N. PD-N.4884. dated November 6, 2020 "On additional measures to improve the education system in Ukraine". <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-5085887>
5. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated September 5, 2018, PD-3931 "On measures to introduce new management principles in the public education system". <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-3893416>
6. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated December 8, 2018 N. 997 "On measures to organize international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in the public education system". <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-4097073>